

INTEGRATE-LMedC

Established Assessment Regime

Work Package 6 - Deliverable 6.1

Project name	INTEGRATE-LMedC
Project acronym	INTEGRATE-LMedC
Project number	101131809
Deliverable no	6.1
Deliverable title	Established Assessment Regime
Contractual delivery month	M06 – June 2024
Responsible partner	Fraunhofer
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Dissemination level	Public
Description of deliverable	Set of defined criteria to assess identified data sources

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DOCUMENT INFORMATION

Document history

Date	Version	Editor	Change	Status
2024-05-24	0.1	Nancy Mah	Initial draft	Complete
2024-06-17	0.2	Nancy Mah	Revised draft including comments by internal review	Complete
2024-06-27	1.0	Nancy Mah	Revised version includes comments from Coordinator	Version for submission to portal

Glossary

Abbreviation / acronym	Description
BBMRI	Biobanking and BioMolecular resources Research Infrastructure
CIOMS	Council for International Organizations of Medical Sciences
DPA	Data Protection Authority
DPO	Data Protection Officer
EBRAINS	European Brain Research Infrastructures
ECRIN	European Clinical Research Infrastructure Network
EDPB	European Data Protection Board
EEA	European Economic Area
EFPIA	European Federation of Pharmaceutical Industries and Associations
EHDS	European Health Data Space
EIRENE RI	Research Infrastructure for EnvIRonmental Exposure assessment in Europe

Abbreviation / acronym	Description
ELSI	Ethical, Legal, and Societal Issues
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EUCROF	European CRO Federation
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable (guiding principles for data management)
IEC	Independent Ethics Committee
LMedC	Large Medical Cohort
PPI	Patient and Public Involvement
RI	Research Infrastructure
SYNCHROS	SYNergies for Cohorts in Health: integrating the ROle of all Stakeholders
UN	United Nations
WHO	World Health Organization
WMA	World Medical Association

1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document describes guidelines for assessing large medical cohorts (LMedC) for their suitability to be included in a future research infrastructure (RI). These guidelines will take into account ethical, legal and societal issues (ELSI), as well as the FAIR guidelines for responsible scientific data management. The present document is the first version of the assessment regime and is considered a working document, which will be updated and refined as INTEGRATE LMedC progresses.

2 INTRODUCTION

The INTEGRATE LMedC consortium was established to develop a new concept to guide and support decision-making for the next-generation research infrastructure (RI) to facilitate efficient utilization and harmonization of large medical cohorts (LMedC) and consequently to accelerate scientific and medical research in Europe and worldwide. Partners include established ESFRI infrastructures such as BBMRI-ERIC, ECRIN, EIRENE, and EBRAINS, as well as additional highly interdisciplinary partners with data management and biobanking expertise. The consortium will take into consideration the users' needs and obstacles for the efficient use of a LMedC RI by performing a gap analysis to identify what is missing from cohort data and samples, RI tools and services, quality measures, and governance models. The consortium will prepare a feasibility study for federated data analysis of LMedC to identify the IT technologies and architecture to ensure appropriate data stewardship and the long-term availability of RIs. A concept outline, including a governance plan and guiding principles for data access and data protection policies, will be developed to ensure the availability of data and samples from LMedC and their subsequent reuse for secondary research. The project will culminate in an overarching RI concept for the management, integration, and sustainability of LMedC studies, along with a financial and operational plan for the implementation of novel service and access possibilities for the research community.

Medical cohorts play a crucial role in advancing both research and healthcare knowledge by providing valuable insights into disease development, progression, and treatment outcomes. These studies refer to a (often large) cohort of individuals who may be followed up over time, collecting detailed clinical, genomic, phenotypic, lifestyle, and environmental/exposure data to better understand the underlying mechanisms of diseases and identify factors that influence health outcomes. By tracking participants' health status and outcomes over extended periods, large medical cohorts (LMedC) enable researchers to uncover associations between various risk factors, biomarkers, and disease outcomes, paving the way for the development of more targeted interventions. Additionally, medical cohorts can serve as powerful platforms for evaluating the effectiveness of healthcare interventions, including new treatments, diagnostic tools (also powered by Artificial Intelligence), and public health-oriented preventive strategies. Thus, by assessing real-world outcomes within and between diverse populations, these studies provide critical evidence to inform healthcare policies, and public health initiatives, ultimately improving health outcomes on a population level.

To ensure the seamless operation of a RI centred on efficient utilization and harmonization of LMedC, guidelines must be drafted to address all aspects of health data sharing, including what health data is shared; how it is shared and overcoming the barriers to sharing. Within WP6 "ELSI, FAIR and fairness", the group will analyse the current and desired states of data sharing and draft possible actions to achieve the desired functionality of the RI, with respect to ethical, legal and societal aspects, as well as the FAIR data principles. In this deliverable, WP6 will outline a series of criteria that large medical cohorts should fulfil for inclusion in future RI for LMedC.

For the purpose of the foregoing, a medical cohort refers to a group of individuals with a shared condition, characteristic of exposure who might be followed over time to collect extensive health-related data and/or biological materials for current and future health research. The data and biological materials collected from a medical cohort are stored as databank and/or biobank collections. In this project, we neither consider interventional clinical trials nor databanks based on health registries without specific follow-up as medical cohorts. The criteria for considering a medical cohort as "large" are the following:

- A clinical cohort comprising over 1000 participants selected for a health condition; or

- A rare disease cohort comprising over 0,5-1% (as a rough guideline) of the total disease population of the country; or
- A population cohort comprising over 10,000 participants.

3 ESTABLISHED ASSESSMENT REGIME

The establishment of an assessment regime for LMedC is the end goal of WP6 and an essential component of the new concept for LMedC relevant for RI. To fulfil this goal, WP6 depends on the work of WP4 (The current European RI-landscape – State-of-the-art) to identify existing RI and their capacities to support LMedC. Within Task 6.1, WP6 will identify data resources from existing RI and analyse the data sharing models and data protection measures, with an aim to map out the ethical and legal challenges for transnational data sharing across institutions. Task 6.2 will examine innovative engagement strategies between different stakeholders for using and sharing assets (data or biological samples). Stakeholders include researchers as consumers of assets, cohort managers as facilitators of assets access, and research participants as the original asset providers. Examples of innovative incentive strategies will be compiled from literature review and use cases within INTEGRATE LMedC, for example, the European Child Birth Cohort Network¹ the International Psychosis Epidemiology Cohort Consortium (IPEC)² and the Human Exposome Assessment Platform (HEAP)³. Finally, over the course of the project, Task 6.3 will develop the assessment criteria for LMedC data sources that are relevant for the future RI. These criteria will focus on ELSI aspects and FAIR, as they pertain to data sharing and data protection. The present document represents the first version of the assessment regime.

3.1 Ethical, Legal and Societal Issues surrounding LMedC

There is a nexus of ethical guidelines and legal policies as well as societal aspects that are relevant for LMedC. This section points out the most relevant ethical, legal, and societal issues (ELSI) for this consortium to date, with a focus on ethical and legal requirements.

Ethical guidelines are “soft laws” meant to protect the human subjects in research projects or clinical trials. Ethical guidelines, such as the Nuremberg Code and the Belmont Report, are universal for all human subjects’ research and have historically been inspired by terrible past human rights abuses. International organizations provide over-arching ethical guidelines in the form of the International Ethical Guidelines for Health-related Research Involving Humans (CIOMS /WHO) and the Declaration of Helsinki (WMA). European initiatives include the Oviedo Convention and its additional protocols (Council of Europe) and the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union. Legal policies such as the European Clinical Trial Regulation (No. 536/2014) further enshrine ethical concepts for human participants in clinical trials. However, the most relevant regulation for EU-based LMedC, is the General Data Protection Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (short GDPR), which directly impacts the processing and sharing of special categories of personal data, such as health data. Furthermore, new regulations in the European Union relevant for EU-based LMedC are designed to enable data-driven innovation by regulating the sharing of public and protected data. These include the Open Data Directive (EU) 2019/1024 and the Data Governance Act (Regulation (EU) 2022/868), which will spur Common European Data Spaces in 14 strategic domains (Agriculture, Cultural Heritage, Energy, Finance, Green deal, Health, Language, Manufacturing, Media, Mobility, Public administration, Research and Innovation, Skills, Tourism). Within the Health and Research & Innovation domains, the European Health Data Space (EHDS) and the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), respectively, will be relevant for a future EU based LMedC RI. As this project is focussing on transnational data sharing across institutions worldwide, also legal frameworks beyond the GDPR should be taken into account. This especially, when applicable to involved LMedC’s and LMedC RI’s for countries outside the EU or international organization with privileges and immunities

accorded under international law (e.g., organizations that are part of the UN System and their Data Protection Framework).

Within the scope of this deliverable, we will focus on data sharing for LMedC and the conditions for operational/practical ethics and legal management and societal aspects.

3.1.1 Ethical Aspects

LMedC data from individuals may have been generated in studies from different contexts, such as publicly funded research projects, or electronic health records. Regardless of the initial context in which the data may have been collected, ethical principles that protect the participants of these LMedC remain the same: autonomy and informed consent, privacy and confidentiality, and beneficence.

Autonomy and informed consent: individuals must be allowed to make their own informed decisions about their participation in a study, and these decisions should be voluntary and free of coercion. Moreover, individuals should be considered as participants of the research and should have an influence on how their assets could be used. Traditional models of “one-time consent” or even “broad consent” may be inadequate for the cohort data in a LMedC RI because: a) the proposed RI aims to share and promote the re-use of data, which are secondary uses whose purpose may not have been covered by the original consent (e.g. secondary use of primary healthcare data); b) advances in technology can lead to unforeseen downstream applications of participants’ assets, which may be ethically controversial. For example, embryoids could be generated from induced pluripotent stem cell – derived germ cells, or human cells could be combined with animal cells to create chimeric brain organoids.

Proposed solutions to address these ethical aspects, in a graded approach would be:

- 1) Dynamic consent: a (digital) platform connects researchers and individual participants in a common space where issues requiring consent or feedback are explained to the participants and participants can ask questions, leading to an “informed” state. Participants can consent or decline novel purposes of re-use or withdraw their consent from an existing purpose.
- 2) Broad consent: broad consent permits the use of the assets for most research purposes, and research participants are not specifically consulted about applications of their assets in studies. However, if the asset is to be used for an ethically contentious research topic, and re-consenting is not possible, case #3 applies.
- 3) Downstream uses are potentially incompatible with informed consent that was initially signed, and re-consenting is not possible: such situations warrant a review by an Independent Ethics Committee (IEC) on a case-by-case basis. The IEC should weigh the balance between advancing medical research for the social good vs. infringing individual rights.

Privacy: As part of the informed consent process, research participants must be informed of the privacy and security measures that are in place to protect their data. It must be explained what the limitations of the measures are and the risks of a privacy invasion, despite data security measures. Furthermore, it must be demonstrated in the consenting process, that participants are aware of these risks; that they have the option to withdraw their data; and that the possibility to withdraw consent is not unduly complex to prevent them from exercising their autonomous decision to do so.

Beneficence: any research carried out using the assets of the participants in the LMedC should: a) provide some kind of benefit, either at the individual level or at the societal level (for example, benefit public health); b) “do no harm” to the participant (i.e, include an inherent risk assessment). An individual benefit could be the return of clinically actionable genetic results to the participant (via

family doctor). For example, a participant's biological material has been genotyped in the context of a new study using the INTEGRATE LMedC RI, and a gene panel reveals that the individual is at high risk for developing a preventable disease in 10 years. This kind of information could be communicated back to the participants, who could start a preventative course of action. At the same time, participants may fear the impact of knowing such information, due to complex implications for themselves and their family members. In such situations, they could exercise their "right not to know". A societal or group benefit from using the individual's data shall always be the goal of LMedC, as integrating data from different cohorts increases the power to reveal underlying insights.

3.1.2 Legal and Regulatory Aspects

Privacy is enshrined as a human right in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (Art. 12) and within the EU in the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union (2012/C 326/02) (Art. 7), in which protection of personal data is covered specifically as well (Art. 8).

With respect to data sharing by EU-based institutes the following data protection regulation is applicable: the European General Data Protection Regulation went into effect on May 25, 2018 and was conceived to harmonize data privacy laws in EU Member States. The Regulation outlines the individual's rights for the protection of personal data. In particular, health data is considered a special category of personal data and requires a higher level of protection. GDPR is relevant for data processing, secure data transfer, data storage, and data access and reuse.

As this project is focussing on worldwide data sharing across institutions including outside of the EU, also other existing legal frameworks governing data protection should be taken into account, if applicable to the involved LMedC and LMedC RI's. For instance, if data sharing involves data protection regulations established by countries outside of the EU, and if an international organization with privileges and immunities accorded under international law is involved in the data sharing, e.g. organizations that are part of the UN System, their own applicable Data Protection Framework will need to be taken into account as well. An example would be the Personal Data Protection and Privacy Principles as adopted by the UN High-Level Committee on Management (HLCM) at its 36th Meeting on 11 October 2018.

Personal data can be defined as "any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person".

Data collection and processing: the participants of the medical cohorts must be informed of the purposes of data processing. Furthermore, as it may not be possible to completely describe the purpose of processing of personal data for scientific research, participants should be allowed to give their consent to certain areas of research. As an example, a research participant may give consent for the user of their data for research into a specific subtype of rare disease (like Emery-Dreifuss muscular dystrophy), but users of a LMedC RI may wish to use the data for a related group of disorders (like laminopathy). If the data are to be processed for a different purpose not declared in the initial consent for personal data collection, the research participant must be notified beforehand, unless the provision of such information proves impossible or would involve a disproportionate effort etc. In such cases appropriate measures shall be taken to protect the data subject's rights and freedoms and legitimate interests, including making the information publicly available. This is an important point for all cohorts in a future RI – as the participants' data could be used for purposes not declared in the original consent, when the data is shared by the RI.

Data transfer: Personal data may be transferred to another country or an international organisation if the receiving institute has provided appropriate safeguards to ensure the safe processing of personal data. The GDPR, national data protections laws from EU Member States, just as data protection frameworks of institutes based outside of the EU or international organizations must be taken into consideration for cross-border data sharing for the purpose of reuse of health data.

However, data protection laws and frameworks should not hinder the regulated flow of personal data within and outside of the EU. The GDPR certainly has global reach and data exchange with Third Countries is often challenging, requiring clear data transfer conditions for both transnational parties, some of which may be included by an adequacy decision for data flow between the EU and non-EU countries⁴. The challenge of transnational data exchange has been assessed by many projects such as the Common Infrastructure for National Cohorts in Europe, Canada, and Africa project (CINECA; EU Horizon 2020), which produced a Catalogue of Canadian, European and African ethical and legal gaps⁵ and concluded that researchers are thus drawn to the use of broad consent and recommends that the use of broad consent for secondary data processing thus still have to be supported by official European guidance.

Data storage: According to worldwide standards on data protection, personal data should only be stored in a form which permits identification of data subjects for as long as necessary for the purposes of the data collection; however, personal data may be stored for longer periods in the context of scientific research purposes, subject to technical and organisational methods to safeguard the rights and freedoms of the research participants. The participant must be informed how long their personal data will be stored.

Data protection by design and default: The data holder is required to implement appropriate technical and organizational measures to safeguard the privacy of the research participants during data processing. This is also known as the “privacy by design” principle. Examples of protective measures include encryption, pseudonymization, anonymization and user authentication. Data that has been anonymized, such that it cannot be used in any way to re-identify a participant, is not regulated by the GDPR or other data protection frameworks, just like data from deceased persons as they no longer fall under the definition of a data subject (ie. identified or identifiable natural person), in the absence of national derogations on the processing of deceased persons’ data⁶.

The European Data Governance Act (Regulation (EU) 2022/868)⁷: The DGA came into force on September 24, 2023 (following a 15-month grace period), with the aim to increase trust in voluntary sharing⁸, availability, and reuse of data for altruistic purposes. The DGA considers both non-personal and personal data. The DGA regulates within the EU the reuse of both publicly available and protected data (including personal data and commercially confidential data) from the public sector, business, and citizens. To facilitate trustworthy data sharing and reuse, the DGA supports the development of Common European Data Spaces in 14 different sectors within the EU. Relevant to the INTEGRATE LMedC are the initiatives around the European Health Data Space and the European Open Science Cloud.

European Health Data Space (EHDS)⁹: The EHDS, currently in a proposal stage, will be a common space where EU citizens can control their electronic health data, as well as share their health data with researchers, innovators and policy makers in a trusted, secure, and privacy-preserving manner. The provisions in the proposed draft EHDS for the secondary use of electronic health data are directly applicable to a future LMedC RI that is based in an EU Member State and subject to EU law.

3.1.3 Societal Aspects

Equity and Fairness: Ensuring equity and fairness in cohort participation and representation is essential to avoid repeating past mistakes (e.g., the concerns raised by the Tuskegee Syphilis Experiment) and exacerbating existing disparities in healthcare and research (e.g., the inclusion of hard-to-reach population groups in population cohorts). Efforts should be made to recruit diverse populations, including underrepresented groups, and address barriers to participation, such as language, socioeconomic status, and accessibility, to promote inclusivity and equity in research participation and benefit sharing.

Equity has a second aspect, not just in terms of representation, but also in terms of technological equity or ‘techquity.’ Techquity, is often described as the intersection of technology and equity and is becoming crucial for LMedC to ensure inclusivity and fairness. Access to technology, digital literacy, and connectivity are key determinants of techquity and by extension to the participation and engagement in LMedCs, influencing the representativeness of study populations and the generalizability of research findings. In terms of inclusivity, leveraging technology can enhance the efficiency, scalability, and reach of LMedC research, facilitating data collection, analysis, and dissemination while minimizing logistical barriers and costs. Embracing techquity principles has been highlighted as a key determinant in the success of healthcare research and delivery by the G20 summit in 2020 and has been included as part of the G20 Riyadh Declaration on digital health.

Community Engagement and Transparency: Engaging with communities and stakeholders throughout the research process fosters trust, accountability, and transparency, and provides the tangible arguments required by policymakers for the long-term support of LMedC. Researchers should involve participants -where possible- in the following aspects: study design, implementation, and dissemination of findings, respecting their input and perspectives. Recent experiences with such community engagement have been positive examples and have been distilled in recommendations put forward by the Common Infrastructure for National Cohorts in Europe, Canada, and Africa (CINECA; EU Horizon 2020), including a Catalogue of Canadian, European and African ethical and legal gaps⁵. Transparent communication about study objectives, procedures, and outcomes builds public trust and confidence in cohort research, strengthening ethical practices and ensuring the responsible use of data for the benefit of society. Therefore, particular attention should be placed on the aspect of trust, due to the duration and potential impact of LMedC findings.

Trust: Building trust with stakeholder groups will be integral to enable data sharing and re-use. The following are a few examples of actions that could help to increase trust:

Researchers / data holders: codes of conduct/practice are instruments that promote consistent, practical guidance in a topic, such that harmonization across institutions could be easier to attain. They can outline the norms, rules, and responsibilities or proper practices in a specific field and be self-regulated. To that end, Regulation 2016/679 introduces codes of conduct as sector-specific compliance tools under Article 40 of the GDPR. The European Data Protection Board (EDPB) specifies strict adherence monitoring requirements elevating the code of conduct, if approval is obtained by a legal tool,¹⁰ to a legal instrument with societal relevance. The final guidelines on codes of conduct for data transfers were adopted by the EDPB in spring 2022. To date, however, no code of conduct has been approved by the EDPB in the health research sector, despite several organisations working on them such as BBMRI¹¹, EFPIA¹² or EUCROF¹³. Most codes are concerned with transfer across EU Member States and do not focus on Third Country aspects. Codes of conduct are also developed on the national level such as in Poland¹⁴ or the Netherlands¹⁵. Both codes are not approved by the national Data Protection Authority (DPA), but already improve the status quo by providing legal guidance to researchers. Also codes that were drafted before the GDPR came into force, such as the “Code of Practice on Secondary Use of Medical Data in Scientific Research projects”¹⁶ showcase the usefulness of such instruments as it provided first guidelines on processing personal (medical) data in collaborative, multiple partner research projects. Adherence to a community-accepted code of conduct has the potential to increase researchers’ trust in the data and their subsequent willingness to reuse datasets.

Participants: public engagement in the form of patient and public involvement (PPI) interactions could help to de-mystify research and empower research participants to get more actively involved in scientific research. Participants should be encouraged to take part in research governance, for example, by becoming members of independent ethics committees or data access committees. This topic is further addressed in Task 6.2.

3.2 Enabling the FAIR principles to optimize data sharing and re-use

The FAIR data principles are a set of guidelines that aim to make data as digital assets automatically machine-actionable, in order to enable machines to find, access, interoperate and reuse data, as well as to support the reuse of data by humans¹⁷. The FAIR principles have been implemented by European RI (for example, BBMRI-ERIC, ELIXIR, ECRIN, EBRAINS, and others), and the principles are promoted for use in the Common European Data Spaces by the DGA. The four guiding principles indicate that data should be:

Findable: In order for data to be reused, it must first be easily findable by humans and machines. Machine-readable metadata are absolutely crucial to enable automatic discovery of datasets. A key issue at this initial stage is the task to annotate data with suitable metadata, which may be registered identifiers or ontologies. Ideally this should be completed at the level of the data source, to minimize annotation errors. Services like FAIR stewardship or high-level tools to generate machine-readable profiles (e.g. Digital Use Conditions Profile Creator¹⁸) will be indispensable at this early stage, as data holders may be inexperienced in transforming their data into a machine-readable form. Furthermore, the choice of controlled vocabularies (registered identifiers or ontologies) for metadata annotation should be standardized to a select number of domain-specific identifiers or ontologies to avoid complications created by mapping between two or more ontologies for the same concepts.

Accessible: The way in which the data can be accessed must be given. Non-proprietary standard communication protocols such as http(s) or ftp should be used to retrieve data. If the data is sensitive (e.g. a special category of personal data according to Art.9 of the GDPR), then an authentication and authorization procedure must be given. For example, access to sensitive genetic data may be granted by a data access committee mechanism, which may require that data requestors submit a data access request to the data holder, either by manual means (email) or through an authentication system like the Life Science Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure (LS AAI).

Interoperable: To reach its full potential, the data need to be easily integrated with other datasets so that data from multiple sources can be seamlessly directed into storage, processing or analysis workflows. The use of a common language for knowledge representation (e.g. JSON LD, OWL, RDF, etc.) facilitates interoperability by generating machine-readable, semantic digital objects of the data. Furthermore, data should meet domain-relevant community standards – if all cohort data are organised in a standard way, using controlled vocabularies and minimal information standards, the data will be readily reused. Examples of data standardization efforts include MIABIS for biobanks¹⁹, the Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership (OMOP)²⁰ for Electronic Health Records (EHR), Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine (DICOM) for medical imaging information²¹, and the Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH)²² for genomic data. All data within the future LMedC RI will need to achieve a high level of interoperability to enable efficient processing and analysis within the RI.

Reusable: The final goal of FAIRification is to optimize data reuse. Besides the elements of technical interoperability described above, end users of data must be able to decide if a dataset is suitable for their purposes. Datasets must be associated with a clear data usage license (e.g. Creative Commons), as organizations may be reluctant to reuse data without clear legal terms. Furthermore, the data provenance, including the whole workflow of data collection, generation, and processing (including compliance with data protection standards) will help users decide if they can reuse the data. Tools to capture elements of data compliance in a machine-readable format are actively being developed²³.

We thus propose to use FAIR-health principles taking quality and ethical/legal considerations into account for the specifications of access regimes in an integrated manner²⁴.

3.3 Assessment of LMedC for an RI

The pre-requisites for managing and distributing data from large medical cohorts must take into account both ELSI and FAIR issues for maximum re-usability and utility, in order to drive innovative medical research within and outside of the EU. It is envisioned that once a large medical cohort has fulfilled the requirements of the assessment regime for an LMedC RI, the cohort will have applicability beyond the EU.

Minimal dataset requirements are guided by recognized standards and/or guidelines. Technical standards for FAIR data could be taken from existing RIs or other initiatives (e.g. ECRIN, BBMRI, HealthData@EU Pilot). The following checklist summarizes the basic criteria for the inclusion of an LMedC into a future RI. The list is not exhaustive and will be expanded and refined during the lifetime of the INTEGRATE LMedC project, as the other work packages progress.

Checklist

Ethics and Informed Consent: participant autonomy and protection of the individual

- Consent elements, as specified by applicable regulations and/or ethical guidelines, such as CIOMS, OVIEDO, Universal Declaration of Human Rights and the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union, are present in informed consent forms and participant information sheets.
 - Voluntary and informed consent, without undue inducement
 - Withdrawal of consent is possible
- Specific provisions of consent are provided
 - Restrictions to fields of research, if any (e.g. only neurodegenerative disease)
 - Who is allowed to use the assets, e.g. academic institutions, for-profit entities, non-profit entities
 - Clear indication on whether commercial exploitation of assets is allowed
- Consent materials presented to participants (e.g. participant information sheet, blank informed consent form, explanatory videos or other media) can be provided
 - Study contact person for questions from participants has been named
- Data protection
 - Contact details of the DPO have been provided
 - Statement that data are treated in compliance with applicable data protection standards
 - Legal basis for data processing is stated, e.g. what will the data be used for and how long
 - Statement on whether data is pseudonymized or anonymized
 - Statement on how special categories of data are handled

Societal Engagement

- Patient Public Involvement: did the project generating the LMedC participate in PPI initiatives?
- Laypersons involved in project governance, e.g. representation on Data Access Committees?

Data Management

- Data holder responsibilities
 - Data license for re-use is clear
 - Dataset is accompanied by a data management plan
 - Data privacy: what measures have been taken to protect the privacy of the individuals in the cohorts, e.g. pseudonymization, anonymization, aggregation, etc.
 - Data security: what measures are in place
 - Governance for data access has been established
 - Data access process is transparent
 - Data Access Request form: standard template can be provided by LMedC RI; ideally it should be in an electronic form and can be used to keep records of data access requests for auditing purposes.
 - Data Access Agreement: standard template can be provided by LMedC RI
 - Data Access Committee established (each cohort should have one)
 - Data Access Committee Code of Conduct: standard template can be provided by LMedC RI

Assessment of FAIRness (suggestions)

- Recommendations on the minimal FAIRness required for LMedC could be guided by the following tools:
 - FAIR Data Maturity Model²⁵
 - FAIRshake²⁶
 - ARDC FAIR assessment tool²⁷
 - FAIR Aware²⁸
 - FAIR Evaluation Services²⁹
 - Semi-automated FAIR assessment workflow³⁰
 - RDA-SHARC Simple Grids³¹
 - HealthyCloud FAIRness assessment tool³²
 - Data Stewardship Wizard³³

Technical implementations to make data FAIR (suggestions)

- A data capture system or data catalogue should fulfill the following criteria:
 - Data should be stored in a way that ensures high integrity.
 - Data should be stored in a system that is appropriate for the type of data, for example, structured data in a database, large files in an appropriate repository (e.g. European Genome-phenome Archive (EGA) for genomic data).
 - The system should allow to record sufficient metadata.
- Preferred ontologies or registered identifiers and mappings (as necessary), some examples:
 - Diseases: ICD-10, MONDO, ORDO
 - Genes: HUGO, NCBI EntrezGene, Ensembl
 - Proteins: SWISS-PROT, Ensembl
 - Data Privacy Vocabulary^{34, 23}
- MOLGENIS³⁵ as an example of a software solution
- DCAT³⁶
- Digital Use Conditions³⁷ / Common Conditions of Use Elements³⁸
- Data Use Ontology³⁹
- Open Digital Rights Language⁴⁰

- Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership (OMOP) Common Data Model (CDM)²⁰

Data Life Cycle

- Cohort data should be assessed in terms of how far it has achieved in each stage of the Data Life Cycle⁴¹: plan, collect, process, analyze, preserve, share and reuse.
 - For example, if data harmonization has already been carried out, the data could already be highly interoperable and a strong candidate for a future LMedC RI. As data harmonization can be very context-specific, the standards used to harmonize the data should be considered. As an example, the harmonization of diagnostic data for rare diseases may require very specific details to make it usable.

4 CONCLUSION

Large medical cohorts are pivotal for advancing medical research, improving public health and operate in a complex legal and ethical regulatory framework. Initiatives like the EHDS, for instance, once fully realised, can significantly enhance the potential of these cohorts by promoting better data sharing, integration, and collaboration. The EHDS is an ambitious initiative by the European Union designed to create a comprehensive framework for the secure and efficient use of health data across Europe. The European Parliament and the Council will adopt the EHDS regulation in the fall of 2024. Secondary use of health data will become applicable in 2028, and clinical trial and human genetic data will be made available in 2030. In alignment with the EU Mission time-frames, the EHDS is expected to become an innovative force five years after applicability. Similarly to the GDPR, the EHDS will have a huge global impact. This could not only accelerate scientific discoveries, genomic research but also contribute to more personalized and effective healthcare solutions. At the same time, the EHDS is one building block in a complex legal framework that comprises the GDPR, AI act or DGA as well as national regulations including biobank laws.

For living up to its potential, it requires projects like INTEGRATE LMedC to conceptualize assessment regimes that meet high level technical standards and national/international ethical/legal requirements. It is thus of utmost importance that these are designed to ensure that what is technically possible today is also ethically sound and legally solid for the research of tomorrow. This requires ensuring ethical and legal compliance by design, whilst following new regulatory initiatives with a risk assessment mindset.

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